

A THEORETICAL STUDY OF PROMOTION POSITIVITY (PROMOTION BASED SELLING) WITH RESPECT TO AN INTERACTION EFFECT ON SALES, USEFUL FOR GENERAL BUSINESS MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

It may be a long permit in business management to think of an individual P and an individual S, in a given business function. Such individual categorization is vital and important to understand behaviour of a business. There should be always an interplay between P and S, on given individual function of P and S. The present study has formulated model on this individuality concern. On the way of its methodology, it has found various insights of business that, if applied correctly, would improve the business more and more. Entire study is theoretically built up with its own methodology to theoretical model formulation that could postulate an advance realism of business controllability without losing business profitability or as such as a revenue making. The study has immense future scopes of research and correctly anticipating a business good enough for present day revenues or profitability ahead.

Keywords: Promotion, Sale, Interaction error and potential, Interaction between promotion and sale, Matrix of the interaction, Ratio of promotion to sale, Change Ratio, Interaction modeling.

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INTRODUCTION

There is always a sort of marketing playing against a sale of business. In no way of non-differences, any business usually gets in touch with marketing prior to happening of sale [Biemans, et al.,2022]. Business with a sale is better said to be the business with marketing. It is a marketing programme of business that a sale must happen, persuasively or rationally [Cruceu, et al., 2014]. This marketing programme, in definition of business, is always treated as improving the business concerned [Rehme, et al., 2012]. This definition of improvement can be replaced by “promotion” as a term because of the fact that promotion could be a better term of marketing as it actually links to objectives of a business, more transparently or in a more resulted way. In this present study, “promotion” would thereby be called instead of “marketing” as the term to use. Moreover, term “promotion” so used in this study should also not mean to “sales promotion” vibe of understanding.

Figure 1.1: Sequential steps of interaction (interaction as process)

Figure 1.2: Interaction relationship (to-and-fro)

Figure 1: Interaction process and relationship

In any business, promotion and sale are two different individual functions of the business [Matthyssens, et al., 2006; Lyus, et al., 2011; Grönroos, 1994; Shen, 2019; Pembu, et al., 2017; Osman, et al., 2011]. Each has unique features of attributes, variables etc. by its individual function. When the two are inter-related to each other, then the inter-relating function can be said as interaction. Figure 1.1 is shown in steps to illustrate a transformation of individuality to interaction. Direction of interaction is to and fro; one is from P to S and other one is from S to P (Figure 1.2). Usually, it is not customary to think that direction is always from P to S. Reverse is also useful and needed, owing to interest of business [HBR, 2006; McColl, et al., 2020].

Table 1: Nature of CR

Sl.	Nature or kind of CR	Feature	Example (Form of CR)
1	Discrete CR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is in integrated form. It can be converted to differential form. Functional conditions are unique. 	P/S or S/P
2	Infinitesimal CR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It's in differential form. It can be converted to discrete form. Functional conditions are unique. 	dP/dS or dS/dP

A Theoretical Study of Promotion Positivity (Promotion Based Selling) With Respect to An Interaction Effect on Sales, Useful for General Business Management

While direction is from P to S, then we can express the phenomenon by ratio P to S due to an effect of S for a cause of P. On the reverse case, the phenomenon should be from S to P owing to cause of S and effect as P. If this is true, then we can express the ratio by discrete or derivative form. So, there could be two kinds of such form. One is discrete and other one is infinitesimal or instantaneous or derivative or differential (Table 1). Let's term the ratio as *change ratio* (CR). Each form is methodological to the interest of the present study.

As explained afterwards in this present study, CR has been found with numerous boundary conditions such as property by range, correction of error, etc. that will ultimately go to result a construction of model, called as CR model of this study. CR model would be helpful to indicate a status of P or S based on given S or P respectively. So, a conversion mechanism does play in the model construction and such mechanism is to-and-fro interaction between P and S. This is interesting about how such a mechanism could exist and dominate to finalize to an interaction result.

Promotion as a function of business may not be required for business, always and it is to be true for sale also [Matthyssens, et al., 2006; Shen, 2019, Osman, et al., 2011]. This means that any business can be run under either P or S. This may be by a suitable combination of both P and S with relative fluctuations [Heinonen, 2018; Fukunaga, et al., 2016; Berger, et al., 2010]. And, a business should be not in existence if it doesn't turn to sale (from profitability, etc.) as its end-point [Lemon, et al., 2016; Turnbull, et al., 1996; Ziliani, 2005; Sharma, et al., 2016].

Which one of P and S is required to be thought of or given an emphasis more may be a background basis of business. Rather, it may sometimes be the need for a joint combination of P and S both, to a given business. In such a combination, sometimes P can be more than S and vice-versa. But, such a combination doesn't exist if an interaction is not in an existence between P and S. This means there may be numerous combinations by relative fluctuations of P and S but only by an interaction, not without it. So, interaction should be treated as a function of management (of business). On this purview, it can also be illustrated that a business without an interaction can be run on. This is possible on individual function of P or S. So, a business can be marketed or made to accomplish its objectives in following two ways -

Way1: Individual P or S (Without Interaction)

Without an interaction, there should be no connection between P and S. At this case, individually both should happen in terms of result or implication. A given business market should prepare its P by without seeking a S level or conversely, anticipate or result to a S without having an effect by P. After happening of S, the business may compare level of S achieved for the given individual P.

Way 2: Interacted P or S (With Interaction)

With an interaction only, there should be a strong connection between P and S. Here, interaction acts as a function resembling to providing an effect onto P as well as S [Naumann, et al., 2020; Ahluwalia, et al., 2000]. Under this effect, of P and S, each loses their individual potential or identity and with an interacted effect, they would result to a level or magnitude. This means that an interaction should only the way or medium which once becomes active would involve together and transform (or a change rather) property of P and S through reaction of interaction. This reaction is to be done by both P and S, not by their individual potential at all but in a shared suitability or contribution (or combination) between them. This shared basis should finally cause the result of interaction in terms of P or S, not restrictively to S always subject to accomplishment of objectives of business.

The present study only explains interacted P or S which constitutes the interaction as a process of to-and-fro nature (Figure 1). Individual P or S and their business achievement is hereby left as future scope of the study. For information, policy making may be the next step after commencement of P or S is accomplished in an interaction business. However, objectives of the study may include the following -

- To explain change ratio (CR) in terms of corrective derivative, property by range, variability by positivity of P or S.
- To describe dominance in terms of CR.
- To illustrate CR model by a given expression of CR.
- To mention various boundary conditions of CR model.
- To mention scopes of work or applicability of CR variability as model.

METHODOLOGY

Cause and effect of promotion are functional to sales. It's vice-versa also. There is no existence of either only, but quite possible though [Camacho, et al, 2022; Heinonen, 2018; Yuan, 2014]. As there should always be an interaction between promotion and sales, such an interaction weighs each (of P and S) to declare a business prevailing under promotion or sales. Depending on nature of business, range of P or S can be fixed upon. This range reflects that at (or with) what vision or mission business is running on. Figure 2 gives (for an illustration) variability pattern of P and S alongwith variability of ratio (dP/dS), where it is shown that S is achieved after long efforts of interaction between P and S, through an alternation of CR (change ratio). Practically, a level of S doesn't come to reality within a shorter time or effort, unless and until P happens or occurs to an accomplishment [Chan, et al., 2023; Leeftang, et al., 2008; Xin, et al., 2016; Mandler, et al., 2021; Day, 2011]. So, there must be a series of P and S occurring in terms of variability profiles (of ups and downs) of P and S, by the interaction.

Figure 2: A typical variation between P and S profiles

Variability profiles of changes in P or S are essential to know in order to decide upon the range fixation of each of P or S. All businesses should never want to remain on a loss unnecessarily [Casais, et al., 2022; Palomino, et al., 2020; Ziliani, 2005]. So, they (marketers) would try maintain a good nature of range within which change-profiles must lie on always (Figure 3.1, Figure 3.2).

Figure 3.1: Variability of dP/dS

Figure 3.2: Variability of dS/dP

Figure 3: Property by range

A Theoretical Study of Promotion Positivity (Promotion Based Selling) With Respect to An Interaction Effect on Sales, Useful for General Business Management

It is also always desired for any business to go with in a healthy and comfort nature of CR over complete life-cycle of the business. There may be an alteration (from dP/dS to dS/dP and vice-versa, for infinitesimal as an example) that should play in a good business. It is also nonetheless to mention that S to be always higher than P may not be a good concept or approach in business.

Alteration to mutual shift from P to S or S to P is an eventual phenomenon of business. It happens. It is good and by virtue of nature of business that is consisted of P and S both. So, there must be possible to generate a model of variability of P and S over an interaction. This model must be in coherence to business by vision, mission and overall objective. There should be a strict eye over inconsistency on this. However, following discussion would explain probable reason of why such inconsistency may occur in the virtue of business and based on this, the model of this present study would be expected to be relying upon.

Functional relations in interaction

As explained of cause and effect phenomenon in any business marketing, P and S can be expressed in an interaction as,

$$P = f(S) \quad \dots \text{(Eq. 1); where, } f = \text{function.}$$

Applying differential derivative,

$$dP = f'(S)dS \quad \dots \text{(Eq.2)}$$

At $S = 0$, $P = \text{constant}$.

At $S = \text{infinity } (\infty)$, $P = \text{infinity } (\infty)$.

Above clarification of range is by Eq.2, shown by Figure 3.1.

Also, as S tends to infinity, P tends to infinity subject to value of $f'(S)$. To get an equal effect of S, P should be calculated with higher values of S to get rid of decreasing tendency of $f'(S)$.

$$\text{Thereby, } dP/dS = f'(S) \quad \dots \text{(Eq.3)}$$

$$\text{Also from Eq.(2), by assuming } f'(S) \text{ as constant, } S = P/f'(S) \quad \dots \text{(Eq. 4)}$$

Above expressions are self-explanatory and Eq.4 is the expression which can be used to proceed further to a model construction of it so as to find out an effect (by profile features of the model, described afterwards) caused by $f'(S)$ in addition to a given function of P in terms of S.

Table 1: Dimensional units (of P and S)[^]

Sl.	P	S
1	Time-valued advertising	Sales budgeting
2	Media (Digital + Printing) value costing	Production output to sales
3	Mass communication budgeting	Revenue of sales
4	Volume of each promotion	Quota sales
5	Spread rate of promotion	Market acquisition rate of sales (or sales growth rate)
6	Qualitative survey of promotion	Segmentation of sales (or sales category)
7	Intensity or depth of promotion	Discounted sales
8	Quota sales promotion	Sales assumptions
9	Resulting or target or accountability of promotion	Resulting or target or accountability of sales

[^]quantitatively (may be in terms of rupee, time duration, unit or volume etc.) and qualitatively (may be in terms of value or image unit, or price or quality-reflective unit or such; also, $4P(+3P)$ of marketing).

After calculating S from Eq.(3), we can determine value of P from the given function, Eq.1, of P. Let's say this is P1. We need to compare, check and validate this new value P (that is, P1) from its earlier value (that is, P). This check or validation should provide a basis of correspondence in the given value of P and new Ps. In fact, such a check would require to correctly obtain the difference between new and old P or S. Such difference is to be towards finding actual potential or variability that business could offer to. So, this indicates a corrective measure which could take place in number of iterations till accomplishment (by P or S) of business. Let's look into it, by the following -

Correction of error

Let, by using Eq.3, first sales is obtained as,

$S1 = S0 + Es$; where $S0$ = given sales (expressed by P of Eq.1 or any assumed value), Es = excess or loss = error.

Then second sales should be as,

$$S2 = S1 + Es = S0 + 2*Es$$

For t-th sales, $St = S0 + t*Es$; t = frequency or number of sales (or promotion) considered.

$$\text{Then, } Es = (St-S0)/t \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.5)}$$

Then, corrected sales for first sales S1 would be as,

$$S11 = S1 - Es \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.6)}$$

And, corresponding "corrected" promotion = $P11 = f(S11)$; other promotions by frequencies can be similarly calculated.

Thereby, correction factor = $(S0 - St)/t$.

As actual sales value always is found to be erroneous, either higher or less, by magnitude as $f'(S)$ causes, of Eq.3, the hype of erroneous increase or decrease, respectively. This problem can be avoided by applying correction factor (Es) as given by Eq.5. It may be research scope to investigate whether Es is related to $f'(S)$, qualitatively or quantitatively, although it's not scope of this present study.

Similarly, above explanations are equally possible to be derived for S with respect to P, as mentioned by following as,

$$\text{Given function of S as, } S = f(P) \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.1a)}$$

$$\text{Or, } dS/dP = f'(P) \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.2a)}$$

At $P = 0$, $S = \text{constant}$.

At $S = \text{infinity } (\infty)$, $P = \text{infinity } (\infty)$.

Above clarification of range is by Eq.2a, shown by Figure 3.2.

Also, as P tends to infinity, S tends to infinity subject to value of $f'(P)$. To get an equal effect of P, S should be calculated with higher values of P to get rid of decreasing tendency of $f'(P)$.

Eq.3, Eq.4, Eq.5 and Eq.6 can be written similarly as, respectively,

$$dS/dP = f'(P) \quad \dots \text{ (Eq. 3a)}$$

$$P = S/f'(P) \quad \dots \text{ (Eq. 4a)}$$

$$Ep = (Pt - P0)/t \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.5a)}$$

$$P11 = P1 - Ep \quad \dots \text{ (Eq.6a)}$$

And, corresponding sales = $S11 = f(P11)$; other sales by frequencies can be similarly determined.

A Theoretical Study of Promotion Positivity (Promotion Based Selling) With Respect to An Interaction Effect on Sales, Useful for General Business Management

In this way, actual P or S can be found out by applying correction and it is interestingly observed from above explanation that actual P or S would somewhat different from given P or S due to prevalence of $f'(P)$ or $f'(S)$ respectively. This is also similarly applicable to instantaneous or derivative form of dP/dS or dS/dP . Having known these (property by range and conditions of error), how CR would form into model, given in further discussion in the present study, would be easily understood. So, applying correction to CR is to be necessary always, be it infinitesimal or discrete. For mentioning, an infinitesimal is a derivative form of discrete nature of CR, always. Similarly, discrete form should constitute of derivative form as well.

Unit of expression

There should be a validation by unit in which P and S are expressed. It is another interesting fact that a correct correspondence of unit is essential and meaningful once both P and S are taken care of positively. This present study is to model CR so the correspondence would satisfy or qualify an expression formed by both P and S. Table 1 gives some of the instances of P and S, which may be used not very orderly manner or serially as they are given in the tabulation, instead they can be used suitably.

Table 2: Dominance and CR

Sl.	Dominance (Or, positivity)	Expression	Functional expression	CR		Conversion
				P/S or dP/dS	S/P or dS/dP	
1	promotion	$P > S$ or, $P-S > 0$	$P > f(S)$	> 1	< 1	Change across dominances is possible from given positivity.
2	sales	$S > P$ or, $S-P > 0$	$S < f(P)$	< 1	> 1	
3	both	$P = S$ or, $S = P$	$P = f(S)$ $S = f(P)$	$= 0$	$= 0$	

Table 3: Outcomes or characters of business (on sales positivity)

Dominance (or, Positivity)	Condition	CR = (dP/dS)	
		Low (availability)	High (demanding)
		Positively favorable	
Sales positivity (S-P > =0)	High (demanding)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Less effective (P to S) • Possibility of revert back • Luxury (Brand) • New product • Competitive product • Emerging market/product • Shut-down product/industry • Inefficient • Blacklisted • Bad imagery product/market/industry • Semi-rigid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highly effective • Well connective (S to P) • Monopoly market, Efficient product/marketing, • Persuasion acquisition is of higher, rapid rate • Consumables • Flexible
	Low (availability)	Negatively favorable	
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extreme scarcity(of resources) • Highly competitive • Highly non-responsive • Rigid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited scarcity of sales • Semi-flexible

Positivity in expression (that is, market dominance condition)

A business can be considered as promotion or sales dominated or both. If it is promotion dominated, then condition would be $P > S$. If it's by sales domination, then condition would be $S > P$. If it is both, then condition be $P = S$ or $S = P$.

For a business (not for industry or market indeed), dominance is important, as applicable to the variability of P and S on their interaction and towards achievement of objective of the business. It is also although possible to have a conversion with respect to given dominance (Table 2). It is observed that a positivity is (to be) maintained in each kind of dominance. And, CR should obey the definition of each and every dominance.

Correlation between CR and Dominance

We should get insight clarifications of business subjected to positivity and CR. His can be achieved by obtaining co-ordination character between them, by range or magnitude. It has been mentioned in Table 3, Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6. In each such tabulation, business characters are specified, to some sort of characterization also. For a positivity to be valid, related concerned variables (P and S) should not change or alter the definition of functional expression. As shown in the tabulations, a high is treated as demanding and low as availability and it is due to the fact that a high value or magnitude is to be the business objective or priority, by positivity, and low magnitude is for mentioning the functional expression of positivity to be at least available without a negativity (as result) or chance of conversion certainly.

Therefore, positivity that may be a business objective should hold a good or healthy range of CR, although conversion to other mode of CR or positivity may be possible at ease.

Table 4: Outcomes or characters of business (on promotion positivity)

Dominance (or Positivity)	Condition	CR = (dP/dS)	
		Low	High
Promotion positivity ($P - S > 0$)	High	Good/Prospective	Sound
	Low	Bad (Inferior)	Interface/Excellent

Table 5: Outcomes or characters of business (on sales positivity)

Dominance (or Positivity)	Condition	Low	High
		CR = (dS/dP)	
Sales positivity ($S - P > 0$)	High	Bad inferior	Well connective/Responsive
	Low	Examining/Testament	Prospective

Table 6: Outcomes or characters of business (on promotion positivity)

Dominance (or Positivity)	Condition	Low	High
		CR = (dS/dP)	
Promotion positivity ($P - S > 0$)	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ending soon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cutting edge profit making Profitable Evolving
	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Obsolete Deadly Dying 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scarcity Saturation

A Theoretical Study of Promotion Positivity (Promotion Based Selling) With Respect to An Interaction Effect on Sales, Useful for General Business Management

Construction of model of interaction growth

This section is to understand rate of change (in percentage) of promotion with respect to sales for a given promotion, through a model construction. This would be useful to anticipate or estimate an effect or effort of promotion towards sales happening, by a magnitude as the result. This is often important for a marketer to correctly go through find out probable sales that a promotion given should exhibit or result to. Also, in several business conditions such as market acquisition, competitive edge making, new business start up, get back up from shutdown etc., it is required to know behaviour of interaction against a given market or industry condition. Let's term such model as CR model or interaction growth rate (I_g) model as the rate of growth (increasing or decreasing) of sales or promotion (as the interaction member) is identified or determined. The model is hereby set up for given variables as mentioned and given by Table 7. For different values of ratio P to S, we can have a chart of values for different magnitude of promotion. Such arrangement can also be true for S to P for values of sales (S). Given the fact of conversion vantage and implication of P to S (to- and fro-) as the fundamental basis of the model, the same chart (Table 7) can be considered to be valid for all CR alongwith dominance or positivity concerns.

The base equation used for the I_g or CR model preparation is given by,

Percentage change (of sales) = I_g = [100*{(P/S) – P}/P] %; where P, S = promotion and sales respectively.

Infinitesimally, percentage change=100*{(dP/dS) – dP}/dP; where dP, dS = differential change of promotion and sales respectively.

where,

P/S = P divided by S = promotion per unit sales = promotion consumed for unit sales of S = f(S)/S = Sales.

P = given promotion so as to cause or correspond to sales (S).

Table 7: Rate of change of CR or interaction growth rate, I_g, (%)

CR (P/S)	Growth rate of interaction (in %) ^ for a given promotion (P) of									
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	0	-50	-67	-75	-80	-83	-86	-88	-89	-90
2	100	0	-33	-50	-60	-67	-71	-75	-78	-80
3	200	50	0	-25	-40	-50	-57	-63	-67	-70
4	300	100	33	0	-20	-33	-43	-50	-56	-60
5	400	150	67	25	0	-17	-29	-38	-44	-50
6	500	200	100	50	20	0	-14	-25	-33	-40
7	600	250	133	75	40	17	0	-13	-22	-30
8	700	300	167	100	60	33	14	0	-11	-20
9	800	350	200	125	80	50	29	13	0	-10
10	900	400	233	150	100	67	43	25	11	0
Determination of components of model ^										
Avg.	450	175	83	38	10	-8	-21	-31	-39	-45
W. Avg.	600	250	133	75	40	17	0	-13	-22	-30
Variance	265028	38917	11077	6069	5917	7003	8361	9698	10926	12028
Standard Deviation	515	197	105	78	77	84	91	98	105	110

^ percentage change = Interaction gradient (%) = Interaction growth rate (%) = 100*{(P/S) - P}/P.

^^ W. Avg. = Weighted Average; Avg. = Average; -ve values are negative sales or promotion indicative whereas +ve ones are positive sales or less promotion indicative.

Figure 5: CR profile or model

It is thereby clear that Ig signifies to a percentage profit over sales against a given promotion. Once plot the values generated by the chart, Table 7, we have the negative values by profile variations that mark the percentage loss as against profit on behalf of a marketing effort to sales profit or loss consideration (Figure 5). So, at one glance and by a singular model operation, we can establish the status of sales profile by CR only. It indicates that a rate of change of CR is possible to be formulated or determined by the expression, of CR model, so applied. Conversely, this implies to CR to be an interaction outcome or effect that is essential to determine its contribution onto budgetary anticipation as well as growth of an interaction between P and S.

Based on the chart-values of Table 7, profiles drawn by microsoft excel spreadsheet are shown in Figure 5. For model construction or implication, two aspects are considered, average and weighted average, whose profiles are the CR model profile. Trend-line expressions have been chosen to define the model profiles set up by W.Avg. and Avg. component. Table 8 shows such model expressions. Thereby, all these findings constitute the components of CR model, or Ig model, able to deliver results of a given P (or S), as responded by an interaction.

Table 8: Profile expressions for Ig model

Profile	Linear Trend Expression	Polynomial Trend Expression
Average	$y = -40.729x + 285.1; R^2 = 0.6539$	$y = 9.8305x^2 - 148.86x + 501.37; R^2 = 0.8977$
W.Avg.	$y = -51.837x + 390.13; R^2 = 0.6539$	$y = 12.512x^2 - 189.46x + 665.38; R^2 = 0.8977$

\hat{y} = interaction growth rate (%); x = magnitude of promotion (P).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the study's explanations and findings, followings can be mentioned against this section –

- With a background aim of impact-giving basis against P and S, the study has achieved its mark to proclaim that the model could be established at ease or even by complexity nature of variability of P and S. Such a study is required when a marketer faces the problem of limiting P or S, with no rigidity upon each of P and S to be continued to. This is a typical business problem that any business must face upon and tries to attempt in several ways without having clear-cut methodology or standard. Such a problem is bound by lamina of vantages which may be shown by an illustration (Figure 6) of interaction matrix so formed in between P and S over positivity. In reality, such implication may be sought for media marketing to modern trading to fundamental business [Yousef, et al, 2021; Khan, et al, 2019; Gupta, et al, 2019].

Figure 6: Interaction matrix: product or business category illustration

- With lots of possibility of model-forming expressions, CR model is found to be of evolving nature. It is due to the fact of –
 - functional representation of P or S in terms of SS or P respectively.
 - selectivity of P or S to be given more emphasis.
- This is quite enhanced or revealed by the fact of $f'(S)$ which causes changing nature to the anticipation of the model result. This is one of guiding criterion in establishing or concluding the CR model.
- Basis of positivity is to be an important selection. So, it needs caring attitude.
- It would be better if the CR model is not operated simultaneously for more than one case of positivity or basis of P or S for a given business.
- Interestingly, the CR model would be able to solve all impending problems of any business related to interaction matrix, given by Figure 6, as well.

CONCLUSIONS

The study has determined variability of Ig by magnitudes of P with an objective of sales (S) only, as shown by Figure 5. This indicates a reverse objective that is only P-based, which can also be possible by the way the study's methodology is described with. Figure 5 shows how a sales-based Ig can provide a basis of understanding to know an effect of P (on sales, S). Such a variability is vital to a marketer's viewpoint and statistics of business objective fulfillments. Interestingly, a business can be improved if its insight voids or flatulency or inefficiency is possible to be measured or taken care of. Description of Es or Ep explains that a given Ig may be improved if the correlation existing between Es (or Ep) with $f'(S)$ (or $f'(P)$) is correctly diagnosed. In fact, a given Es is to be always in a fight to become more improved, over the existence or prevailing effort of $f'(S)$ for a given set of functional variables or attributes of (mathematical) function of S.

As this ultimately accounts to having a value of I_g , such corrections that may be a research scope also, must be maintained properly.

Interplay or interchange of P to S or S to P in a given E_s or E_p should be always kept in mind in order to define the study more useful, suitable, reliable, and meaningful. In this, correspondence on the interplay (between P and S) must be checked always by units (of expression; Table 1) in a given functional relationship between P and S for business objectives to be fulfilled.

As one of basic insights of the present study is dominance, so there is the scope to determine an individual magnitude (of P or S) which often found as “unable to even touch or so” in functional relationship between P and S can be expressed mathematically by whatsoever interplay that is governing. This signifies to the realm outcome of the study and that is for an example a determination of P with positivity of P but in terms of S in the functional relationship. Such as example is possible practically or rationally, so is explained in this study by its own methodological way and explanations (please refer to Table 2 to Table 6 and Figure 6 in this).

The entire study must be not restricted to product or service business only, but it can explicitly be applicable to find out an industry competence in a given set of companies or competitions in a given business market (Figure 6). Suitably and obviously, expression for model generation of I_g (for P and S) can take an use of P or S status of competitions on similar markets or businesses. So, the present study is appropriate for product (by class or category) as well as to a business market by industry as a status.

I_g model is significant to evaluate efficiency or effectiveness of a business system, to negotiate with various attributes or business variables as attached to with P or S. It can also help provide ways to avoid ongoing or upcoming business problems or cutting-edge competitiveness or a profitability status of business means.

I_g model can provide a virtual realization (or platform) of P and S by its I_g value and such virtuality can advance or make business smarter by gaining competitive profitability stay ahead in the business by using its own data-set of magnitude (as shown in Table 7, Figure 5) for a given promotion. Such a study can clearly view over various “functional” variables that are inferior or damaging to business growth. It can have also the level of compatibility of accommodation in a more rapid or swift manner into model magnitude regulation and determination. However, the I_g model can be enhanced more by incorporating several initiatives such as enterprise planning, feedbacks or reviews of customers, survey data etc. and etc. In all, the study should provide a platform to controllably execute or accomplish a business objective with all required business maneuverability.

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A Theoretical Study of Promotion Positivity (Promotion Based Selling) With Respect to An
Interaction Effect on Sales, Useful for General Business Management

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